

Deliverable D1.1

Project Logo, Website, and Social Media

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Change Log

Version	Date	Author	Description of changes
v1	16.06.2025	Rafael Diaz, Nancy Aguirre-Velásquez	Initial draft

Acronyms and Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
JPG	Image file format, stands for Joint Photographic Experts Group
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
PNG	Image file format, stands for Portable Network Graphics
PU	Public
SVG	Image file format, stands for Scalable Vector Graphics
v	Version
WEBP	Image file format, stands for Web Picture
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

Acronyms and Abbreviations	1
Executive Summary	3
1. Introduction	4
2. Description of work	4
2.1. Branding	4
2.1.1. Logo	4
2.1.2. Guidelines	6
2.1.3. Dissemination	8
2.1.3.1. Website	8
2.1.3.2. Social media channels	10
2.1.3.3. Zenodo	10
3. Conclusion	10

Executive Summary

RE-IMAGINE-CROPS is a technology development project from the Horizon Europe Work Programme, under the European Innovation Council (EIC) Pathfinder Call. It brings together 9 partners from 5 countries in a 3 million EUR effort over 3 years.

This document outlines the guidelines for the Project Logo, Website, and Social Media. A subsequent report on the Exploitation Plan, along with the Dissemination and Communication Plan, will be shared in deliverables D1.3 and D1.5, respectively (month 6).

The project website is under development and will be publicly accessible via a subdomain of the Euro-Biolmaging ERIC website in mid-July, 2025. It will serve as the primary information hub for both internal and external stakeholders. A comprehensive branding identity, including guidelines for public representation, is provided herein. Additionally, the project's social media presence is outlined, with details on the official handles across various communication platforms.

1. Introduction

The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project is part of the European Innovation Council (EIC) through the Pathfinder Open Call and is led by the project coordinator, Euro-Biolmaging. The consortium is a partnership of 8 beneficiaries, with representation of Austria, Italy, Finland, France, and the Netherlands. The project started on 1 May 2025 and continues until April 2028.

RE-IMAGINE-CROPS seeks to transform agricultural practices through innovation in Digital Precision Agronomy. The primary objective of the project is to develop the first mobile imaging technology for in-field measurement of biophysical processes in crops, thereby enabling more effective crop management practices.

This deliverable is part of Work Package 1, on “Coordination and Outreach”. Reaching our key stakeholders and the general audience is key to supporting our aim to further develop and innovate in Digital Precision Agronomy practices. The website, general logo, and social media channels of the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project are described hereafter.

2. Description of work

2.1. Branding

The branding of a project is key for ease of recognition and dissemination of a coherent message. The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS branding package provides the consortium members with a set of assets to facilitate the communication of the project with internal and external purposes.

2.1.1. Logo

The project logo features a leaf-shaped droplet, symbolising plant biology. Within the leaf, a branch-like structure reflects the plant anatomy, while also evoking a circuit of sensor pathways. A yellow dot is also present in the logo, in the topmost section, which signifies a tracer particle, hinting at the imaging processes involved in PET imaging. Below the leaf droplet, a semi-circular arc with five dots is shown, representing a detector ring also featured in the PET imaging detection instrument.

The logos are available in PNG, JPG, WEBP, and SVG formats and are stored in the project’s *Google Drive*.

RE
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The logo must always include a clear space when in use, shown as follows:

In addition to the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS logo, the project partners are also aware of their obligation to acknowledge EU funding and to display the EU emblem in all information and communication materials.

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2.1.2. Guidelines

Proper usage of the project logo is encouraged. Any modifications or alterations are not permissible, as a coherent identity is easier to share and to follow. The following are examples of alterations that are not permitted:

The logo can be used in one color shade.
Use only Primary Color: #0C6E59

The logo can't use different colors from the colors panel.

Don't stretch the logo.

Don't stretch the logo.

The color palette for the logo, shown below, includes 3 primary colors, 3 secondary colors, and 6 extra colors for accents.

PRIMARY COLORS

SECONDARY COLORS

HEX #0C6E59
RGB 12 110 89
CMYK 86 30 67 22

HEX #08403F
RGB 8 64 63
CMYK 90 46 58 56

HEX #FFF812
RGB 255 248 18
CMYK 8 0 88 0

HEX #052D2B
RGB 5 45 43
CMYK 90 52 63 70

HEX #0F936D
RGB 15 147 109
CMYK 82 17 67 3

HEX #00E599
RGB 0 229 153
CMYK 65 0 57 0

EXTRA COLORS

HEX #3c3056
RGB 60 48 86
CMYK 84 85 35 32

HEX #9775a7
RGB 151 117 167
CMYK 48 59 10 0

HEX #10a6a9
RGB 16 166 169
CMYK 75 9 36 0

HEX #76dbd3
RGB 118 219 211
CMYK 52 0 25 0

HEX #df524a
RGB 223 82 74
CMYK 6 79 67 0

HEX #e59270
RGB 229 146 112
CMYK 8 50 55 0

The project's chosen fonts are Figtree for titles and DM Sans for texts (both provided by fonts.google.com).

HEADING TEXT, SEMIBOLD

Revealing the Unseen: Illuminating Life through Bioimaging

HEADING TEXT, MEDIUM

A curious cat named 3 whiskers roamed the 7 hills of Xanadu, exploring the mysteries of pi (π) and the infinite possibilities hidden within the realm of alphanumeric characters.

Figtree (fonts.googlecom)

BODY TEXT

Bioimaging is a revolutionary field at the intersection of biology and imaging technology, providing invaluable insights into the intricate structures and dynamic processes within living organisms. Through the lens of cutting-edge imaging techniques, scientists delve into the microscopic realms of cells, tissues, and entire organisms, unraveling the mysteries of life at the molecular level.

A curious cat named 3 whiskers roamed the 7 hills of Xanadu, exploring the mysteries of pi (π) and the infinite possibilities hidden within the realm of **alpha-numeric** characters.

DM Sans (fonts.googlecom)

2.1.3. Dissemination

The project dissemination will take place through different channels. Internal dissemination among the members will be via scheduled meetings, whereas external dissemination will be deployed throughout online presence and a few in-person events, with the website being the first contact point for our partners and external members.

2.1.3.1. Website

The project website, hosted under the domain of the Euro-BioImaging general website (re-imagine-crops.eurobioimaging.eu, currently under development), serves as the primary source of information for partners, stakeholders, and all interested members of the general audience. The website will change throughout the progress of the project and is expected to feature news,

interviews with members of the project team, and lay summaries of key events, including stakeholder workshops with the on-focus group discussions. Major achievements or relevant news will be published within regular newsletters for the Euro-BioImaging stakeholders.

An official launch is scheduled for mid-July, with a corresponding mention in the project's social media channels.

A few snapshots of the preliminary version of the website are shown below:

2.1.3.2. Social media channels

The coordinator, Euro-Biolmaging ERIC, is highly active on social media, usually sharing around 1 publication per week. The LinkedIn and X profiles from the RI have amassed followings of nearly 6000 and 5500 members, respectively. A RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project account is now active on LinkedIn and BlueSky, and they will serve as the main Social Media channels that will feature the progress of the project. Together with the coordinator's Social Media presence, both channels will be used to reach the community of potential users. The partners should reach out to the coordinator for any posts they wish to publish on the accounts. Partners can link the project with the handle @reimaginecrops or hashtag #reimaginecrops. The EC Communication toolkit recommends the partners to tag them in the posts by using the following handle and hashtags: @EUeic, #EUeic, and #eicPathfinder.

The selected channels were based on their popularity among professionals and bioimage enthusiasts, as well as Euro-Biolmaging's involvement in those channels.

The social media account handles are the following:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/re-imagine-crops/>
- BlueSky: <https://bsky.app/profile/re-imagine-crops.bsky.social>

2.1.3.3. Zenodo

All public deliverables and materials will be published in the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS Zenodo page, under the Euro-Biolmaging ERIC account:

- Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/re-imagine-crops/>

3. Conclusion

The current RE-IMAGINE-CROPS website, logo, and social media report outline the communication guidelines for representing the project to the general public, with the aim of raising awareness and ensuring consistent, high-visibility outreach in a coherent and coordinated manner.

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The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project has received funding from the EIC Pathfinder Open program under grant agreement ID 101187260. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.